

The Analysis of Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of leadership and organizational culture on employee performance through work motivation as an intervening variable. The population in this study was Executing Examiners at one of the Bekasi Customs and Excise Offices, totaling 143 people. Based on the Slovin formula, the number of samples taken was 60 people. The sampling technique in this study uses probability sampling, with the simple random sampling method. The data analysis technique uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. The results showed that: 1) Leadership has a direct and significant effect on work motivation, 2) Organizational culture has no direct effect on work motivation; 3) Leadership, organizational culture, and work motivation have a direct and significant effect on employee performance; 4) Work motivation variable is able to mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance; 5) Work motivation variable is not able to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is important in an organization's efforts to achieve its goals. In an organization, employees are one of the most important resources. It can be said that the employee's job performance is very necessary because, through the performance of this job, people will know the extent to which that employee is able to perform assigned tasks and responsibilities. Therefore, to enhance optimal performance, it is necessary to establish a clear standard, which requires defining clear, measurable criteria so that it becomes a benchmark to jointly define. (Paramitha dkk., 2019).

As in the case of one of the customs and excise offices in Bekasi, various innovations and improvements have been made to improve service performance and control. Many factors can be used to improve employee performance. Organizations will take various measures to ensure that employees can work optimally. Some factors that can improve employee performance include leadership, organizational culture, and work motivation.

Leadership is the ability to influence others. A leader's success depends on their ability to influence. Leadership is an important factor in organizations, where leaders are expected to be able to provide direction to employees, especially in times of openness. Therefore, the leadership needed is leadership that empowers employees. One of the most difficult challenges leaders often face is how to mobilize their employees so that they are always ready to use their full potential to serve the organization.

Organizational culture plays an important role in the organizational environment, where it will influence many factors. Organizational culture is an invisible social force that motivates organizational members to participate in professional activities. In public organizations, an organizational culture that is appropriate and compatible with personal characteristics can create a sense of comfort for employees and will gradually increase their commitment to the organization. Motivation is very important for employees because the level of incentive is a measure of employee performance, so if the system provided by the organization is fair enough to employees, it will encourage employees to do well. better than your work and more responsible to everyone. . assigned tasks. Employees who are highly motivated at work will be encouraged to work more enthusiastically and can contribute positively to the work that has become their responsibility. Highly motivated employees have high performance (Amalia et al., 2016).

Based on the description above, the purpose of this study is to determine the effect of leadership and organizational culture on employee performance through work motivation as an intervening variable.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Leadership is the means by which a leader influences, directs, encourages and controls his or her subordinates, expressed in the form of behavioral or personality patterns, and so that the subordinates can perform their work effectively. conscious and voluntary way to achieve goals. A leader is someone who has an agenda and behaves towards group members using a certain method or style, so that the leader acts as a dynamic force that

encourages, motivates and coordinates the company in achieving predetermined goals. (Paramitha S., 2019) . Some previous studies related to the influence of leadership on employee motivation and performance have been conducted by: Chen et al., (2022); Dash (2022); Ouyang (2022); Ronald (2021); Smama'h et al., (2023); Lolowang et al., (2019); Rino (2017); Pracoyo et al., (2022); Juwaini et al., (2021); Haji (2018), research results show that leadership has a significant effect on employee motivation and performance. However, this is different from the results of research conducted by Basir et al (2023), where the research results show that leadership has no effect on employee performance.

Organizational culture is a value that grows and develops within an organization and is realized and implemented by members who determine the function and identity of the organization (Paskauli & Andreani, 2019). Organizational culture is a pattern of organizational beliefs and values that is understood, imbued and practiced by the organization, so that this pattern gives its own meaning and becomes the basis for rules of behavior in the organization. Therefore, organizational culture is used as a controller and direction in shaping human attitudes and behavior in the organization. Several previous studies related to the influence of organizational culture on employee motivation and performance were carried out by: Hajj (2018); Lolowang et al., (2019); Rino et al., (2017); David (2020); Al-Musadieg et al (2018); Makhmut et al., (2023); Pracoyo et al., (2022); Juwaini et al., (2021); Mulyana et al., (2021); Maria (2019), research results show that organizational culture has a significant effect on employee motivation and performance. However, this is different from the results of research conducted by Al-Musadieg et al., (2018); Maria (2019), research results show that organizational culture has no effect on employee work motivation.

Work motivation can be interpreted as a person's strength which can give rise to a level of persistence and enthusiasm in carrying out an activity, whether originating from within the individual himself or from outside the individual (Rismayadi & Maemunah, 2016). How strong an individual's motivation is will determine the quality of behavior he displays, both in the context of studying, working and in other areas of life. Several previous studies related to the influence of motivation on employee performance were carried out by: Al-Musadieg et al., (2018); Basir et al., (2023); Ingsih et al., (2021); Lolowang et al., (2019); Rino et al., (2017); Juwaini et al., (2021); Kumari et al., (2023), Maria (2019), research results show that motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. However, in contrast to the results of research conducted by Mulyana et al (2021), the research results show that motivation has no effect on employee performance.

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the research conceptual framework above, the research hypothesis is as follows:

- a. Ha1: It is suspected that leadership has a direct and significant effect on employee work motivation.
- b. Ha2: It is suspected that organizational culture has a direct and significant effect on employee work motivation.
- c. Ha3: It is suspected that leadership has a direct and significant effect on employee performance.
- d. Ha4: It is suspected that organizational culture has a direct and significant effect on employee performance.
- e. Ha5: It is suspected that work motivation has a direct and significant effect on employee performance.
- f. Ha6: It is suspected that leadership influences employee performance through work motivation as an intervening variable.
- g. Ha7: It is suspected that organizational culture influences employee performance through work motivation as an intervening variable.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a type of quantitative research that is associative in nature. Data sources are obtained from primary data and secondary data. The population in this study were 143 Executing Inspector Employees at one of the Bekasi Customs and Excise Offices. Based on the Slovin formula, the number of samples taken was 60 people. The sampling technique in this research uses *probability sampling*, with a *simple random sampling method*. *Simple Random Sampling* is taking sample members from a population randomly without paying attention to the strata in the population. The data collection techniques use interviews, questionnaires and documentation.

Research variables consist of independent, dependent and intervening variables. The leadership independent variable indicator (X1) is adapted from Handayani (2021), namely: Have a vision; Able to make strategic planning; Integrity; Ability to influence others; Ability to give examples; Ability to make decisions; Ability to communicate effectively; Able to develop a team; Transparency; and Goal oriented. Indicator of the independent variable organizational culture (X2) based on Edison et al., (2016), consisting of Self-awareness; Aggressiveness; Personality; Performance; and Team orientation. The indicators for the intervening variable work motivation (Y) were adapted

from Briandana *et al.*, (2019), namely: Organizational policies; Leadership Quality; Interpersonal relationships with leaders; Interpersonal relationships with subordinates; Relationships with colleagues; Decent salary; Job security; Personal life; Working conditions; and Status. Meanwhile, the dependent variable indicator for employee performance (Z) refers to research conducted by Ilham, (2022), namely: Quality of work; Work quantity; Implementation of duties and responsibilities; Lots of work; Arrival on time; and Established cooperation. This research uses a 1-5 Likert scale measurement scale. The data analysis technique uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Structural model testing in PLS was carried out with the help of Smart PLS version 3.0 software.

RESULTS

Composite Reliability

The composite reliability value can be used to test the reliability value of each indicator on a variable . If the Composite reliability value is above 0.70 it can be said to be good.

Table 1. Composite Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability
Leadership (X1)	0.926
Organizational Culture (X2)	0.924
Work Motivation (Y)	0.931
Employee Performance (Z)	0.890

Source: SmartPLS 3.0 output

Table 1 shows that the Composite Reliability value for all variables is greater than 0.70, which means that the variable is able to meet Composite Reliability or in other words the indicators and constructs that form them are consistent.

R-Square Analysis

R-square is a measure of the proportion of variation in the value of the variable that will be influenced, namely endogenous, that can be explained by the variable that influences it, namely exogenous.

Table 2. R-Square Value

Variables	R-Square
Work Motivation (Y)	0.338
Employee Performance (Z)	0.635

Source: SmartPLS 3.0 output

Based on the Smart PLS 3.0 output, it produces an R-square value as shown in Table 2. Table 2 shows that leadership and organizational culture on work motivation have an R-Square value of 0.338, meaning that leadership and organizational culture are able to explain employee work motivation by 33.8% while other variables are none in this study, the remaining 66.2%. Furthermore, the leadership model, organizational culture, and work motivation on

employee performance have an R-Square of 0.635, meaning that 63.5% of leadership, organizational culture, and work motivation are able to explain employee performance and the remaining 36.5% explains other variables that are not in the research.

Hypothesis test

This test is to determine the path coefficients of the structural model. The goal is to test and analyze the significance of all relationships or hypothesis testing. The path coefficient results are as follows:

Figure 2. Results of Path Coefficients

Table 3. Path Coefficients

Variable Relationships	Original Sample	T-Statistics	P-Value	Information
X1 => Y	0.480	4,476	0,000	Ha1 accepted
X2 => Y	0.168	1,204	0.229	Ha2 is not accepted
X1 => Z	0.338	3,813	0,000	Ha3 accepted
X2 => Z	0.328	4,157	0,000	Ha4 accepted
Y => Z	0.316	3,705	0,000	Ha5 accepted
X1 => Y => Z	0.151	3,002	0.003	Ha6 accepted
X2 => Y => Z	0.053	1,076	0.283	Ha7 is not accepted

Based on the table above it can be explained as follows:

- The calculated t value of leadership (X1) on work motivation (Y) is 4,476 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, meaning that leadership (X1) has a direct and significant effect on work motivation (Y). Leadership (X1) has a direct influence on work motivation (Y) of 0.480.
- The calculated t value of organizational culture on work motivation (Y) is 1.204 with a significance value of 0.229 > 0.05, meaning that organizational culture (X2) has no direct effect on work motivation (Y). Organizational culture (X2) has a direct influence on work motivation (Y) of 0.168.

- c. The calculated t value of leadership (X1) on employee performance (Z) is 3,813 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning that leadership (X1) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). Leadership (X1) has a direct influence on employee performance (Z) of 0.338.
- d. The calculated t value of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Z) is 4,157 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning that organizational culture (X2) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). Organizational culture (X2) has a direct influence on employee performance (Z) of 0.328.
- e. The calculated t value of work motivation (Y) on employee performance (Z) is 3.705 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, meaning that work motivation (Y) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). Work motivation (Y) has a direct influence on employee performance (Z) of 0.316.
- f. The calculated t value of leadership (X1) on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y) is 3.002 with a significance value of 0.003, meaning that leadership (X1) has a significant effect on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y). Leadership (X1) has an indirect influence on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y) of 0.151.
- g. The calculated t value of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y) is 1.076 with a significance value of 0.283, meaning that organizational culture (X2) has no significant effect on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y). Organizational culture (X2) has an indirect influence on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y) of 0.053.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research results, the research discussion can be explained as follows:

The influence of leadership (X1) on work motivation (Y)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha1 is accepted and proven to be true, namely leadership (X1) has a direct and significant effect on work motivation (Y). This means that the better the attention of employee leaders in carrying out all work, the more employee motivation will increase in working. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rino (2017); Hajj (2018); Lolowang et al., (2019); Ronald (2021); Chen et al., (2022); Dash (2022); Ouyang (2022); and Smama'h et al., (2023), research results show that leadership has a significant effect on work motivation.

The results of this research are supported by the opinion of Danim (2017) who states that the presence of a leader enables employees to be motivated to work effectively and efficiently with certain accountability, that leadership means the ability to motivate, how leadership is capable of motivating subordinates so that employees are truly called upon to do their work. So it can be concluded that leadership has a direct and significant effect on work motivation, the better the leadership is at providing attention, encouraging and

caring for employees, the higher the work motivation will be so that organizational goals can be achieved optimally.

The influence of organizational culture (X2) on work motivation (Y)

Based on the research results, the hypothesis Ha2 is not accepted, namely organizational culture (X2) has no direct effect on work motivation (Y). The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Al-Musadieq et al., (2018); Maria (2019), research results show that organizational culture has no effect on employee work motivation. This could be caused by a lack of understanding of organizational culture, which will influence but not significantly affect employee work motivation.

The results of this research are not in line with the theory put forward by Wirawan (2015), one of the roles of organizational culture is motivation. Improving organizational culture will motivate employees to achieve organizational goals. With a strong organization, culture creates a common understanding among employees, so that the organization achieves organizational goals.

The influence of leadership (X1) on employee performance (Z)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha3 is accepted and proven to be true, namely leadership (X1) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). This means that the better the employee's leadership pays attention to carrying out all work, the more the employee's performance will improve. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rino (2017); Lolowang et al., (2019); Ingsih et al., (2021); Juwaini et al., (2021); and Pracoyo et al., (2022), research results show that leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

The results of this research are supported by the opinion of Dewi (2021), stating that leadership factors are closely related to how a leader communicates his thoughts and ideas as stated in the planned annual targets and achievements. This greatly affects employee performance. So it can be concluded that leadership has a direct and significant effect on employee performance. The better the leadership is in providing attention, encouraging and caring for employees, the higher the employee performance will be so that organizational goals can be achieved.

The influence of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Z)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha4 is accepted and proven to be true, namely organizational culture (X2) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). This means that the better the organizational culture implemented by employees, the better employee performance will be. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rino et al., (2017); Al-Musadieq et al (2018); Lolowang et al., (2019); Mary (2019); David (2020); Juwaini et al., (2021); Mulyana et al., (2021); Pracoyo et al., (2022), and Makhmut et al., (2023), research results show that organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance.

The results of this research are supported by the opinion of Rijanto & Mukaram (2018), stating that organizations in improving employee performance need to create a good organizational culture so that the organization can achieve the desired goals. A strong organizational culture will support the development of employee performance and motivate employees to achieve common goals. In the end, it will shape employee behavior in a certain direction as desired by the organization. So it can be concluded that organizational culture has a direct and significant effect on employee performance, the better the implementation of organizational culture, the higher employee performance at work so that organizational goals can be achieved.

The influence of work motivation (Y) on employee performance (Z)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha5 is accepted and proven to be true, namely work motivation (Y) has a direct and significant effect on employee performance (Z). This means that the better the employee's motivation at work, the more employee performance will improve. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rino et al., (2017); Al-Musadieq et al., (2018); Mary (2019); Lolowang et al., (2019); Ingsih et al., (2021); Juwaini et al., (2021); Basir et al., (2023); and Kumari et al., (2023), research results show that work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance.

The results of this research are supported by the opinion of Hasibuan (2018), stating that one of the factors that influences employee performance is performance motivation. Motivation is a condition that encourages employee independence to achieve organizational goals. Employees who have high motivation at work will certainly have a high awareness of being accountable for their work. The higher the level of employee work motivation, the better their performance will be, employee work motivation can be increased in various ways. So it can be concluded that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The higher the work motivation, the more optimal employee performance will be.

The influence of leadership (X1) on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha6 is accepted and proven to be true, namely leadership (X1) has a significant effect on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y). This means that motivation variables are able to mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Rino et al., (2017); and Lolowang et al., (2019), research results show that work motivation variables are able to mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance. These results indicate that employee work motivation appears as a variable that is able to mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance. This means that leadership indirectly produces good employee performance and is able to foster employee work motivation to improve performance.

The influence of organizational culture (X2) on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y)

Based on the research results, hypothesis Ha7 is not accepted, namely organizational culture (X2) does not have a significant effect on employee performance (Z) through work motivation (Y). This means that motivation variables are unable to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Daud (2020), the results of the research show that work motivation variables are unable to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. Lack of employee understanding of organizational culture can have an indirect impact on decreasing employee performance and reducing employee work motivation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the following conclusions are obtained from this research: Leadership has a direct and significant effect on work motivation; Organizational culture does not have a direct effect on work motivation; Leadership, organizational culture, and work motivation have a direct and significant effect on employee performance; The work motivation variable is able to mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance; The work motivation variable is unable to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. Suggestions for future researchers are that researchers can develop this research by examining other factors that can influence employee performance increasing the sample size and using different analytical tools.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

It is hoped that this research can be developed by other researchers, by adding variables, different research company, and different analytical tools, the results of this research can be useful for educational people who like to write and this article can be used as a reference in the field of human resource management.

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